
Impact of E-Resources on The Reading Habits of Undergraduate Students of Kittel Arts College, Dharwad

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of electronic resources on the reading habits of undergraduate students at Kittel Arts College, Dharwad. E-resources, encompassing e-books, online journals, databases, and digital archives, have reshaped how students access and interact with academic content. Using structured questionnaires, data were collected and analysed through descriptive methods. Findings indicate a predominant preference for e-resources over traditional printed materials, attributed to their convenience, accessibility, and diverse content availability. The study underscores a growing trend toward digital reading and suggests enhancing e-resource access, promoting digital literacy, and advocating regular reading benefits. These insights can aid institutions in fostering supportive digital learning environments for academic success.

Keywords

E-Resources; Reading Habits; Undergraduate Students etc.

Electronic access

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1. INTRODUCTION

E-resources (electronic resources) refer to any type of digital material or content that is accessible via electronic devices such as computers, tablets, or smartphones. These resources are typically used for academic, professional, or personal purposes and are available in various formats like text, audio, video, and interactive media. E-resources can include:

- i. **E-books:** Digital versions of printed books, which can be read on electronic devices such as e-readers, tablets, and computers.
- ii. **E-journals:** Online versions of scholarly and academic journals that provide access to research articles and papers.
- iii. **Databases:** Collections of organized information, such as bibliographic databases (e.g., PubMed, JSTOR, Scopus), which users can search to find academic papers, research, and other relevant data.
- iv. **Online articles:** Articles published on websites or platforms that are accessible via the internet, ranging from news outlets to specialized blogs.
- v. **Websites:** Online platforms offering resources like research materials, educational content, or other professional and academic tools.
- vi. **Audio-visual materials:** Digital videos, podcasts, or webinars that can be used for learning or entertainment purposes.
- vii. **Online Courses:** Digital learning resources offered through platforms like Coursera, edX, or YouTube, which include video lectures, assignments, and interactive learning tools.

E-resources offer the advantage of being easily accessible, often updated regularly, and available across different platforms, making them an essential tool in education, research, and everyday life.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

This study explores the impact of E-Resources on the reading habits of Undergraduate Students of Kittel Arts College Dharwad. The objectives of the study are:

1. To understand the reading habits of the respondents.
2. To know the frequency of use of library resources by the respondents.
3. To ascertain the usage of electronic resources in the library by the respondents.

4. To know the impact of electronic resources on the reading habits of the respondents.
5. To understand the problem faced by the respondents in making use of resources.
6. To suggest measures to improve the reading habits among the respondents

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

To determine the sample size, the study used the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula for sample size. Among the total size of 729 units, 266 units were selected for the study. Calculations yielded a required sample size of 248, given a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 0.05. However, the final sample size exceeds this estimate, totalling 266 undergraduate students. For the present study, a survey research method along with simple random sampling has been adopted. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The target population for the present study constitutes the Undergraduate students of Kittel Arts College, Dharwad. This study is based on primary data; the researcher collected data from the respondents. After the collection of questionnaires, the data have been evaluated and presented in the proposed study.

Population of the Study:

Total strength of Kittel Arts College

First year	241
Second Year	244
Third Year	244
Total	729

4. SCOPE AND LIMITATION:

The scope of the present study is limited to Undergraduate Students of Kittel Arts College, Dharwad, which is affiliated to Karnatak University, Dharwad. This study explores the reading habits among the Undergraduate students of Kittel Arts College, Dharwad.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

5.1 Age-wise Distribution

Table 5.1 shows that the majority of respondents are young adults, with 78.9% of the participants aged 18-19. A smaller group, 18%, falls within the 20-21 age

range, which cumulatively brings the total percentage of respondents under 22 years old to 97%. Only 1.5% of the participants are aged 22-25, and another 1.5% are over 25 years

Table 5.1: Age-wise Distribution

Age	Respondents	%
18-19	210	78.9
20-21	48	18.0
22-25	4	1.5
Over 25	4	1.5
Total	266	100

5.2 Gender- wise Distribution

Table 5.2 reveals that a strong majority of male respondents, with 80.5% identifying as male. Female respondents make up only 19.5% of the sample.

Table 5.2: Gender wise Distribution

Gender	Respondents	%
Female	52	19.5
Male	214	80.5
Total	266	100.0

5.3 Year-wise Distribution

Table 5.3 reveals that the sample is heavily concentrated on the first year, with 74.4% of respondents identifying as first-year students. This indicates that the data primarily reflects the perspectives of those early in their academic journey. The second and third years are represented by smaller groups, at 9.8% and 14.3%, respectively, while fourth-year students are the least represented, making up only 1.5% of the sample.

Table 5.3: Year-wise Distribution

Year	Respondents	%
First year	198	74.4
Fourth year	4	1.5
Second year	26	9.8
Third year	38	14.3
Total	266	100.0

5.4 Frequency of Use of E-Resources

Table 5.4 depicts that a large majority of respondents, 78.2%, read daily, indicating that frequent reading is

a common activity among the majority of students. A smaller portion, 15%, read several times a week, adding to the overall regular readership. However, there is a small minority—2.3% each—that reads once a week, rarely, or never, making up 7% of the sample combined. This indicates that while the vast majority have a strong habit of reading for pleasure, a very small group engages in leisure reading infrequently or not at all.

Table 5.4: Frequency of use of E-Resources

Frequency	Respondents	%
Daily	208	78.2
Never	6	2.3
Once a week	6	2.3
Rarely	6	2.3
Several time a week	40	15.0
Total	266	100.0

5.5 Time Devoted for E-Resources

Table 5.5 analyses the data on the number of hours spent on reading E-Resources per week. The majority of respondents, i.e. 35.3%, spend between 1 and 3 hours per week reading, while a notable 28.6% dedicate more than 6 hours to reading every week. A smaller portion, 23.3%, engages in reading between 4 to 6 hours per week, while 12.8% of respondents spend less than 1 hour reading each week.

Table 5.5: Time Devoted to E-Resources

Particular	Respondent	%
1-3 hours	94	35.3
4-6 hours	62	23.3
Less than 1 hour	34	12.8
More than 6 hours	76	28.6
Total	266	100

5.6 Awareness and Use of E-Resources

Table 5.6 shows that fiction is the most popular choice, with 37.6% of respondents indicating it as their preferred genre. Newspapers and magazines are also commonly enjoyed, with 22.5% and 21.8% of respondents selecting them, respectively. Non-fiction materials, such as biographies and essays, are chosen by 9.8% of the sample, while online articles are the least favoured, with only 8.3% of respondents selecting them. This indicates that while a variety of reading materials are enjoyed, fiction, newspapers,

and magazines are the most preferred among the respondents.

Table 5.6: Awareness and Use of E-Resources

Types of E-resources	Respondents	%
Fiction (e.g. novels, short stories)	100	37.59
Non-fiction (e.g. biographies, essays)	26	9.77
Magazines	58	21.8
News Papers	60	22.55
Online articles	22	8.27
Total	266	100

5.7 Preferred Medium of Resources

Table 5.7 reveals that a strong preference for printed books, with 70.7% of respondents indicating that this is their preferred format. E-books and online articles are less popular, chosen by 8.3% and 9.0% of respondents, respectively. Audio books are the least favoured, with only 4.5% of respondents selecting this option. Additionally, 7.5% of participants chose "other," indicating some may have unique preferences not covered in the listed options.

Table 5.7: Preferred Medium of Resources

Medium of Resources	Respondents	%
Audio books	12	4.5
E-books	22	8.3
Online articles	24	9
Other	20	7.5
Printed books	188	70.7
Total	266	100

5.8 Location of Accessing E-Resources

Table 5.8 shows the majority of respondents (69.2%) typically read in a library café, indicating that this setting is the most popular choice for reading. College spaces also serve as a common reading spot, with 25.6% of participants select this option. Other locations such as the bedroom, regular cafes, and outdoors are much less frequently chosen, with only 1.5% selecting the bedroom and café each, and 2.3% choosing outdoor spaces like parks or buses.

Table 5.8: Location of Accessing E-Resources

Location	Frequency	%
Library	184	69.17
Home	4	1.50
College	68	25.56
Cafe	4	1.50
Outdoors (e.g., park, bus)	6	2.25
Total	266	100.0

5.9 Awareness of the E-resources in the library

Table 5.9 shows that the majority of respondents (63.2%) are fully aware of electronic resources, indicating that most students are knowledgeable about the library's digital offerings. A smaller portion, 24.8%, are somewhat aware, indicating that they have limited knowledge but may be familiar with some of the available resources. However, 12% of respondents are not aware of the library's electronic resources at all, highlighting a gap in awareness.

Table 5.9: Awareness of the E-resources in the library

Aware of e-resources	Respondents	%
Not aware	32	12.0
Somewhat aware	66	24.8
Yes, fully aware	168	63.2
Total	266	100.0

5.10 Purpose of Library Visit

Table 5.10 shows that data on the primary purpose of library visits. The majority of respondents (75.9%) visit the library for studying or research, highlighting that the library is primarily seen as a place for academic work. A smaller portion, 11.3%, visit the library to borrow books, while 8.3% use electronic resources during their visits. Only 4.6% attend events or workshops at the library, indicating that while events are offered, they are not the main draw for most students. Overall, the library is primarily utilized as a study and research space, with secondary functions like borrowing books and using electronic resources also being important

Table 5.10: Purpose of Library Visit

Purpose	Respondents	%
Attending Events/Workshops	12	4.6
Borrowing Books	30	11.3
Studying/Research	202	75.9
Using Electronic Resources	22	8.3
Total	266	100.0

5.11 Types of Most Frequently Used E-Resource

Table 5.11 depicts the data on platforms used for accessing e-resources in the library. The college library websites are the most commonly used platform, with 47.4% of respondents relying on it for accessing digital resources. Online databases are the second most popular option, used by 27.8% of participants, followed by Google Scholar, which is used by 20.3% of respondents. E-book platforms are the least favoured, with only 4.5% of participants using them. This indicates that while the library's own website and online databases are the primary sources for e-resources, Google Scholar also plays a significant role in academic research, while e-book platforms are less commonly used.

Table 5.11: Types of Most Frequently Used E-Resources

E-resources	Respondent	%
College library website	126	47.36
Online databases	74	27.81
Google Scholar	54	20.30
E-book platforms	12	4.51
Total	266	100.0

5.12 Electronic Gadgets used for accessing e-resources

Table 5.12 shows the data on preferred for accessing electronic resources. Smartphones are the most popular choice, with 42.1% of respondents using them for this purpose. Desktop computers are the second most preferred option, with 31.6% of participants selecting them. Laptops are also commonly used by 21.8% of respondents, while tablets are the least favoured, chosen by only 4.5%. This indicates that mobile devices, particularly smartphones, are the most convenient and preferred

platform for accessing e-resources, followed by desktop computers, while tablets see limited use.

Table 5.12: Electronic Gadgets used for accessing e-resources

Electronic Gadget	Respondent	%
Desktop computers	84	31.6
Laptops	58	21.8
Smartphones	112	42.1
Tablets	12	4.5
Total	266	100.0

5.13 Satisfaction of respondents on the use of E-Resources

Table 5.13 reveals the data on overall satisfaction with the libraries electronic resources with a mixed response. A combined 59.4% of respondents report being either "Very Satisfied" (26.3%) or "Satisfied" (33.1%), indicating a generally positive perception of the resources available. However, there is a significant portion of dissatisfaction, with 9.8% expressing "Dissatisfied" and 27.8% being "Very Dissatisfied." Only 3% of respondents felt neutral about their satisfaction. This indicates that while many students are content with the library's electronic resources, there is a notable group who are dissatisfied, highlighting areas for potential improvement in the library's digital offerings.

Table 5.13: Satisfaction of respondents on the use of E-Resources

Satisfactory Level	Respondents	%
Very Satisfied	70	26.3
Satisfied	88	33.1
Neutral	8	3.0
Dissatisfied	26	9.77
Very dissatisfied	74	27.81
Total	266	100.0

5.14 Impact of Electronic Resources

Table 5.14 deals with the analyses of data on the impact of e-resources on access to a wide variety of reading materials, showing a predominantly positive response. A majority of respondents (51.1%) agree that e-resources have increased their access to diverse

reading materials, while 24.1% strongly agree. Together, these two groups make up 75.2% of respondents, indicating that most students perceive e-resources as a valuable tool for expanding their access to reading materials. However, a smaller portion of respondents are neutral (18.8%), and even fewer disagree (5.3%) or strongly disagree (0.8%). The table reveals that most find e-resources beneficial; there is a small segment that either does not feel the same way or remains indifferent.

Table 5.14: Impact of Electronic Resources

Impact	Respondents	%
Strongly Agree	64	24.1
Agree	136	51.1
Neutral	50	18.8
Disagree	14	5.3
Strongly Disagree	2	.8
Total	266	100.0

5.15 Convenience of E-Resources over Traditional Printed Materials

Table 5.15 reveals mixed opinions. A majority of respondents (41.4%) agree that e-resources are more convenient for reading, while a smaller proportion (1.5%) strongly agree. However, a significant portion of respondents remain neutral (28.6%) and around 15.8% disagree with the statement. And 12.8% respondents strongly disagree, indicating that for some, e-resources are less convenient than printed materials.

Table 5.15: Convenience of E-Resources over traditional printed materials

Impact	Respondent	%
Agree	110	41.4
Disagree	42	15.8
Neutral	76	28.6
Strongly agree	4	1.5
Strongly disagree	34	12.8
Total	266	100.0

5.16 Satisfaction of users in accessing e-resources

Table 5.16 analyses the data on whether reading time has increased because of using e-resources, showing a generally positive response. A total of 38.3% of respondents agree, and 6.8% strongly agree that their reading time has increased due to e-resources.

Together, these groups account for 45.1% of the total respondents, indicating that a significant portion of students feel that e-resources have encouraged more reading. However, 30.1% of respondents remain neutral, and 12.8% disagree or strongly disagree, indicating that for some, e-resources have not led to an increase in reading time. This highlights that while many students benefit from the convenience of e-resources, others may not experience the same effect.

Table 5.16: Satisfaction of users in accessing e-resources

Satisfaction level	Respondent	%
Agree	102	38.3
Disagree	34	12.8
Neutral	80	30.1
Strongly agree	18	6.8
Strongly disagree	32	12.0
Total	266	100.0

5.17 Satisfaction of accessing e-resources over traditional printed materials

Table 5.17 shows a strong preference for e-resources. A significant 47.4% of respondents agree, and 18.8% strongly agree that they prefer e-resources over printed materials. Together, this accounts for 66.2% of respondents, indicating that most students favour digital reading formats. However, 27.1% are neutral, and only 6.8% respondents strongly agree, this table indicates that while e-resources are popular, a small group still prefers traditional printed materials or has no strong preference. This highlights the growing trend towards digital reading, though printed materials continue to have some appeal

Table 5.17: Satisfaction of accessing e-resources over traditional printed materials

Satisfaction level	Respondent	%
Agree	126	47.4
Disagree	14	5.3
Neutral	72	27.1
Strongly Agree	50	18.8
Strongly Disagree	4	1.5
Total	266	100.0

5.18 Satisfaction of accessing e-resources in the future

Table 5.18 provides the data on the anticipation of shifting reading habits toward e-resources in the future with a strong tendency towards digital reading. A total of 52.6% of respondents agree, and 19.5% strongly agree that they expect their reading habits to shift more towards e-resources in the future. Together, this accounts for 72.1% of participants, indicating a clear expectation that e-resources will play a larger role in their reading habits going forward. However, 21.8% are neutral, and only a small portion (6%) disagrees or strongly disagrees, indicating that while many anticipate a shift, there are still some who may not be as inclined to make that change

Table 5.18: Satisfaction with accessing e-resources in the future

Satisfaction level	Respondent	%
Agree	140	52.6
Disagree	12	4.5
Neutral	58	21.8
Strongly Agree	52	19.5
Strongly Disagree	4	1.5
Total	266	100.0

6. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- i. The survey revealed that 78.9% of respondents are aged between 18–19, with 97% under 22. Males dominated the sample (80.5%), while females accounted for 19.5%.
- ii. First-year students made up 74.4%, followed by third-year (14.3%), second-year (9.8%), and fourth-year (1.5%) students. A significant 78.2% read daily for leisure, 15% read weekly, and only 7% rarely or never read.
- iii. Most of the respondents spend 1–3 hours (35.3%) or over 6 hours (28.6%) reading weekly, while 12.8% read for less than an hour. Fiction (37.6%), newspapers (22.5%), and magazines (21.8%) were preferred, unlike non-fiction and online articles.
- iv. The respondents favored printed books (70.7%), while e-books (8.3%) and audiobooks (4.5%) were less popular. Most read in the library (69.2%) or college spaces (25.6%), with few choosing bedrooms or outdoor areas.

- v. Around 45.1% read for 1–2 hours per session, while 30.1% read for 30 minutes. For academics, 60.9% used e-resources daily, 22.6% weekly, and a minority rarely used them.
- vi. While 63.2% knew about library e-resources, 12% were unaware. Most visited the library to study (75.9%), while only 11.3% borrowed books, and 8.3% used e-resources.
- vii. The college library website was most used (47.4%), followed by databases (27.8%) and Google Scholar (20.3%). E-book platforms were the least utilised (4.5%).
- viii. About 41.4% found e-resources more convenient, while 28.6% were neutral or they disagreed. Additionally, 45.1% agreed that e-resources increased reading time, whereas 25.8% disagreed.
- ix. A majority (51.1%) of the respondents were satisfied with the e-resources' impact on reading habits, 30.1% were neutral, and 18.8% expressed dissatisfaction.
- x. Nearly 70% would recommend e-resources to enhance reading habits, while 24.8% were neutral, and only 6.1% disagreed.

7. CONCLUSION:

To enhance reading engagement among undergraduate students, this study recommends providing a diverse selection of appealing materials while emphasizing the benefits of reading, particularly for occasional readers. For time-constrained students, setting manageable reading goals and offering content aligned with their interests can boost participation. Libraries should expand their collections to include popular formats like fiction, newspapers, and magazines while also increasing digital options such as e-books and audiobooks to cater to different preferences. Additionally, creating more comfortable and quiet reading spaces in libraries, cafés, and outdoor areas can improve the reading environment. To encourage longer reading sessions, institutions should offer both engaging long-form content and easily digestible short reads. Finally, promoting e-resources through training and improved accessibility remains crucial, especially for students who currently use them infrequently, ensuring that digital and traditional reading methods coexist to support varied learning styles and preferences.

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